

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities / IPBES transformative change assessment (4.2)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address a wide range of challenges and obstacles that impede transformative change toward a sustainable world for nature and people, with a focus on strategies to overcome them in order to advance global, regional and local visions for a sustainable world for nature and people. The chapter provides evidence on political, social and economic inequalities, among and within countries. In this context, a review of literature focused on power imbalances and inequalities was conducted and is further described below.

The goal of the review was to “test” some major statements and arguments from the chapter’s first draft, with a focus on those related to political economy to feed into section 4.2.2 and 4.2.3. By doing so, the hope was also to begin to assess confidence in these arguments. Statements include: “Neoliberal (re)structuring of state policies, including liberalization and austerity, limits transformative change for biodiversity restoration and conservation” and “Corporate power and lobbying limits transformative change”.

Process overview

Protocol

Process 1 – Testing statements through keyword based literature searches

Keyword searches related to the statement were then used. Some of them were also used to feed the analysis in challenge 3 – section 4.2.3. Because “biodiversity loss” is not always included in the literature, keywords associated with sectors known to be leading drivers of biodiversity loss, such as, mining, forestry, agribusiness, extractivism, oil and gas, land use change, habitat destruction, habitat loss, degradation were used in the search.

Coordinating lead authors, lead authors and contributing authors provided supplementary references from their own knowledge and areas of expertise.

Details search 1 on investment agreements as a barrier to transformative change:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((investor-state dispute) AND (oil OR gas OR mining OR coal OR agriculture OR extractivism OR fossil fuel OR biodiversity))
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 27 records **(A)**. Of these 27 total results, 7 articles reappeared under different keyword searches. Logging, drilling, land use planning, forestry, agribusiness, pipeline, soy and palm oil generated no results.
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded and abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.
- **Sample extracted:** 9 relevant records **(B)**.
- **Treatment applied:** Alongside searches on the Web of Science database, grey literature to find more solution-focused articles for the brief was also searched for. This grey literature search generated eight articles. Five of these articles by searching for the name of the publishing institution — UNCTAD, the Transnational Institute (TNI), Third World Network and the Bretton Woods Project — and “investor-state dispute” on Google. The Reyes (2020) and Muchhala (2022) articles were also added to the list. The last piece of grey literature — the one by Arato et

al. — was found by Googling “investor state dispute reform.” All but the Bretton Woods Project article were found on 8 May 2023 (the Bretton Woods Project piece was found on 9 May 2023).

Details search 2 on ecologically-damaging subsidies persisting despite international commitments for reform:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((subsidies) AND ((Biodiversity AND agribusiness) OR (Biodiversity loss AND deforestation AND international) OR (biodiversity loss AND fossil fuels) OR (biodiversity loss AND oil)) OR ((lobbying AND biodiversity) OR (transnational corporations AND biodiversity) OR (lobbying AND agriculture AND deforestation)))
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 211 total results (**C**), with 38 repeats among other (trade agreement) searches and 2 repeats from the (investor state dispute) search. 34 references considered relevant.
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.
- **Sample extracted:** 27 highly relevant (**D**), 66 marginally relevant.

Details search 3 on the State glass ceiling:

Statement: “The State has a glass ceiling that impedes transformative change”

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((glass ceiling) AND (environmental state OR environment))
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023

- **Sample extracted:** 83 total results (**E**), no repeats. 6 references considered relevant (**F**).
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.

Details search 4 on trade agreements as a barrier to transformative change:

Statement: "Trade agreements can act as a barrier to transformative change"

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((trade agreement) AND (oil OR gas OR mining OR coal OR agriculture OR extractivism OR fossil fuel OR biodiversity OR deforestation OR drilling OR soy OR palm oil OR land use planning OR forestry OR pipeline OR agribusiness))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 213 results total (**G**). 34 relevant results (**H**).
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.

Details search 5 on anti-politics:

Statement: "There is a form of anti-politics that impedes transformative change"

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((anti-politics) AND ((oil OR gas OR mining OR coal OR agriculture OR extractivism OR fossil fuel OR biodiversity OR deforestation OR drilling OR soy OR palm oil OR land use planning OR forestry OR pipeline OR agribusiness)))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 18 total results **(I)**, with 4 repeat results. Coal, soy, palm oil, fossil fuel and agribusiness searches generated no results. 5 references considered relevant **(J)**.
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.

Details search 6 on greenwashing:

Statement: "Greenwashing and/or voluntary mechanisms can act as a barrier to transformative change."

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((greenwashing) AND (environmental policy OR biodiversity OR nature-positive) OR ((voluntary mechanisms) AND (biodiversity)))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 47 total results **(K)**, no repeats. 12 references considered relevant **(L)**.
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:

- Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
- Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
- Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
- Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.

Details search 7 on lobbying:

Statement: “Corporate power via lobbying as a barrier to transformative change

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based literature search
- **Search terms:**

((lobbying) AND (biodiversity) AND {regulatory capture) AND (transnational corporations AND biodiversity) AND (agriculture AND deforestation) AND (agriculture AND land use change) OR (energy policy OR climate policy OR environmental policy AND revolving door))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Date:** May, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** The search returned 99 results (**M**), with 25 labelled highly relevant (**N**) (with one repeat) and 18 marginally relevant.
- **Treatment applied:** articles were downloaded into spreadsheets. The abstracts were then screened with the following questions:
 - Does the article shed insight into a barrier of transformative change? (e.g., does it help us understand what is getting in the way of widespread biodiversity conservation/sustainable use?)
 - Does the article demonstrate how power operates in relation to efforts towards transformative change?
 - Highlighted green = highly relevant
 - Highlighted yellow = marginally relevant
 - No highlighting = not relevant
 - Second screening: A second person reviewed the coding and made adjustments, or flagged articles for discussion.
 - Green articles underwent full review and insights were drawn up into short briefings that focused on barriers and overcoming challenges.

Web of Science’s returns were limited in scope. For example, the most fruitful Web of Science search “biodiversity loss AND subsidies” primarily returned relevant results surrounding agriculture, with few

articles addressing energy, mining and petroleum subsidies. However, as addressed on page XVIII of the 2019 IPBES Global Summary, subsidies to the energy and mining industries, including fossil fuels, represent a major driver of biodiversity loss. Related WoS keyword searches “biodiversity loss AND fossil fuels” and “biodiversity loss AND oil” yielded only five total “highly relevant” articles. While this may represent a limitation of the search terms, meta-analyses of literature review methodologies have found Google Scholar to return larger quantities of relevant citations than WoS, especially in the social sciences and humanities (Martín-Martín et al, 2018).

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(A)	CSV	160 KB	List of records from Scopus search on investment agreements as a barrier to transformative change
B	2_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(B)	CSV	16 KB	List of references selected from Scopus search on investment agreements as a barrier to transformative change
C	3_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(C)	CSV	502 KB	List of records from Scopus search on ecologically-damaging subsidies
D	4_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(D)	CSV	51 KB	List of references selected from Scopus search on ecologically-damaging subsidies
E	5_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(E)	CSV	149 KB	83 records from WoS State glass ceiling search
F	6_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(F)	CSV	8 KB	6 relevant records from WoS State glass ceiling search
G	7_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(G)	CSV	343 KB	213 records from WoS search on trade agreements
H	8_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(H)	CSV	59 KB	34 relevant records from WoS search on trade agreements
I	9_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(I)	CSV	91 KB	18 total results from WoS search on anti-politics
J	10_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(J)	CSV	8 KB	5 relevant references from WoS search on anti-politics
K	11_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(K)	CSV	189 KB	47 total results from WoS search on greenwashing
L	12_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(L)	CSV	17 KB	12 relevant references selected from WoS search on greenwashing
M	13_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(M)	CSV	198 KB	99 total results from WoS search on lobbying
N	14_IPBES_TCA_4.2_11-2023_(N)	CSV	49 KB	25 selected relevant references from WoS search on lobbying